

**FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIC GOALS IN
THE SUCCESSFUL DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTIONS.**

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Annotation: This article aims to distinguish the strategic divisions of institutions in the field of higher education in the competitive environment, to determine its goals and potential, to develop some problems and their solutions, to prepare appropriate recommendations and put them into practice.

Key words: higher education, management, strategy, competition, project, matrix, external environment, internal environment, leadership, education, organization.

The country's education policy is characterized by the preservation of the traditional foundations of the education system and, at the same time, the multifaceted diversity of the education system, the combination of state and non-state education structures, which creates a competitive environment.

In the competitive environment in the field of educational services, it is especially important to rationally approach the choice of the strategy of a modern higher education institution that provides a number of educational services to various groups of the population. The basis for developing the strategy of a higher education institution in a competitive environment is to determine its goals and potential. When defining the general goal, the main direction of the activity of the higher education institution, as well as the principles of its work in the external environment both in the country and abroad, business relations, cooperation with other higher education

institutions, working with regions, attitude to the consumer, organizational culture, traditions, climate in the team should be taken into account. will have to be taken into account.

The general goal of state higher education institutions is to maintain the capacity to produce and provide high-quality educational services to consumers based on the use of modern educational technologies.

The following should be taken into account when making a strategic choice:

- requirements for the quality of education;
- requirements for the quality of the teacher;
- the condition of the material and technical base of the higher education institution;
- motivation of teaching staff;
- the quality of educational programs and other educational and methodological developments;
- quality of students;
- infrastructure quality;
- quality of knowledge;
- innovative activity of management;
- introduction of technological innovations;
- demand for graduates;
- risk of lack of demand for educational services;
- rational placement of personnel, distribution of tasks;
- providing connections between subsystems of the higher education institution and management of these connections;
- the results of analysis and control for making quick management decisions aimed at correcting the strategy, taking into account the influence of external and internal environmental factors.

An important step in the development of the strategy of a higher education institution is to analyze the gaps between the intended goals and real opportunities and to determine the ways to solve them.

It should be noted that the goals of the higher education institution can be adjusted based on the results of a comprehensive analysis of the external environment and its internal capabilities. The selection of organizational goals is the first and most important decision in strategic planning. They serve as guidelines for all subsequent stages of planning and, at the same time, set certain restrictions on the direction of the organization's activities in the analysis of development alternatives.

There are few formal procedures for selecting targets and they change less frequently than strategies. World experience allows us to distinguish one of the most successful algorithms for the formation of organizational goals, consisting of six stages.

Consists of realizing the importance of formulating and presenting goals as a prerequisite for the successful development of a higher education institution. The most common mistake in choosing organizational development goals, in our opinion, is treating them as something specific and predetermined. Therefore, most organizations do not have clearly defined and documented goals.

Organizations that do not discuss common and business goals lose the ability to achieve agreement among employees on common development goals. A key rule in selecting goals, especially shared goals, is to involve employees in the development and open discussion of alternatives. It creates the conditions for uniting the majority of employees around a common goal and shows others that they can look for opportunities to meet their economic and social needs in other organizations.

In order to form the strategic goal of the organization, it is important for the management of the organization to have a vision, that is, ideas about the current state

of the organization, how it will be in the future, what it strives for, how it will benefit society. The organization's goals are designed to support a common goal (mission) and are proportionate to it.

In order to form a whole set of organizational goals and not to miss the important ones, it is recommended to first distinguish the strategic divisions of the higher education institution and determine the important functional directions, which are called the goal directions of the organization. That is, services, personnel management and promotion, scientific research, external and internal communications, supply, finance, etc. Essentially, it is necessary to identify the functional areas in which management plans to achieve significant change.

1. Logical construction of goals. At this stage, all the goals of the higher education institution are logically connected to a certain system.

Here it is decided to ensure mutual support of the main task-goals, and this, in turn, serves as a condition for their achievement. For example, increasing the level of PVK is related to goals and can be supported by them. Development of a new product sample and improvement of the production management system.

2. Involvement of employees in the formation of goals. A goal in which the employees of the organization actively participated in the development unites them and serves as a strong motive for further actions to achieve it. Success in this work will be more noticeable if each goal is accompanied by a specific plan of actions aimed at achieving the goal, with deadlines for their implementation and personal responsibility of each employee.

3. Visual presentation of goals. Clarity and visual presentation of goals is important not only for the organization's employees, but also for its consumers and the general public. Clearly formulated and visually presented goals help unite employees, increase reputation and create a positive image of the organization. The visual representation of the goals can be an arrangement, a plan, symbols that give a more concrete and figurative idea of the company.

4. Creating a "target portrait of the organization". In conclusion, it is useful to paint a purposeful portrait of a higher education institution.

To do this, it is recommended to invite employees to fill out a questionnaire reflecting their ideas about the company. The choice of goals is greatly influenced by the personal values and goals of the organization's employees. First of all, the opinion and values of the top management of the company and the owner are taken into account. Top management maintains a long-term commitment to certain values, which is reflected in the choice of the type of management, as well as in the goals of the organization.

The strategic direction of modern education is the individual himself, all his unique motives, needs, interests. In the new century, the living conditions of humanity require the transition to a new knowledge-based strategy for the development of the entire society, a prospective educational system that meets this goal, information and high-performance technologies.

At the same time, it does not mean a break from the adaptation of education to new conditions - the prevailing cultural and educational models and ideals. A certain degree of conservatism of the existing educational systems, careful and careful intervention in their improvement and reform is also desirable. It should be noted that the strategic, long-term goals and objectives of education are expressed in the principles of the state education policy, legal documents regulating the educational process. In the competitive environment, many higher education institutions are actively developing innovative activities, which allows to adapt to changes in the external environment by updating knowledge, developing and applying new educational technologies.

Making changes in a higher education institution involves the implementation of the following steps:

- analysis and forecasting of the influence of external factors;
- change planning;

- development and adoption and implementation of management decisions;
- evaluation of the effectiveness of changes.

At the same time, providing innovative projects with a modern level of management is the most important requirement in higher education institutions, as well as in other organizations of the educational system.

An innovation project can be seen as a transformation process, type of activity and business area. The innovative project aims to develop theoretical and practical issues related to the creation, distribution and application of new technologies and new educational services. The implementation of an innovative project is associated with the risk of lack of demand, the need for a minimum period of time between the decision on the innovative project and its implementation. The rational choice of the organizational structure of the project is one of the main conditions for its effectiveness. A matrix organizational structure is chosen for the management of innovation projects for the following reasons:

- it allows to determine the current status of many projects;
- helps in the preparation of various projects, as well as in resolving conflicts between the functional roles of individual departments;
- increases the flexibility of the project management system;
- allows management to better control employees;
- allows to clearly define the goals of the project, its status and difficulties;
- the whole project team works together;
- allows qualified specialists to work on several projects at the same time within the scope of their professional powers;
- ensures the growth of the number of leadership positions in the organization, promotes the improvement of cross-functional relations and disseminates information between different departments and groups working on the project.

At the same time, it is impossible not to take into account some weaknesses of the matrix structure of the organization. If the official reporting line is established

at the same administrative level as the network management, "dual reporting lines" may develop. With a matrix structure, more interpersonal relationships are required. It is often difficult for a project manager to assess the contribution of each project participant. Executives and project managers may report to different bosses. Many performers can participate in the preparation and implementation of innovative projects.

Therefore, it is important to clearly divide responsibilities in the overall process of managing an innovation project in order to avoid conflicts that may arise in the matrix structure due to the functions of each leader in decision-making. When choosing a project management structure, it is important to ensure efficiency in decision-making and, on this basis, to achieve the efficiency of innovation. It is necessary to rationalize the management structure, to ensure the effective use of specialists within the framework of the selected project structure. For optimal decision-making, it is important to combine forms of documents and rationalize information carriers, workflow schemes, data processing systems. Heads of departments appointed by the organization's top management can act as innovation managers. Senior management reviews program projects for the development of new educational services and the introduction of new educational technologies. When forming innovative projects, management should take into account their characteristics and effectiveness. Top management must create an environment where new ideas and new products are an integral part of the organization's culture and style. The success of an innovation project depends on the effective cooperation of project managers and specialists. To organize the effective work of the team, it is necessary to ensure the correct ratio of pedagogical and pedagogical assistants. Professional direction, formal and informal relationships in the team, dominant motives in it, and the relationship between the team members themselves and the leader should also be taken into account.

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